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Evaluation & Impact Assessment

PRACTICING EVALUATIVE THINKING

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING ADDRESSING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Throughout the process with completion of a self-assessment template by the facilitator at the end.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>One person, implemented by a single facilitator/actor.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1 hour and practiced periodically.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Self-Assessment Template.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 16, 19, 20.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

THE EVALUATION FACILITATION BRITTLESTAR

Image source: Katherine Hough (www.katherinehaugh.com)

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Embed evaluative thinking throughout the interactive innovation process.
- Support the facilitator to think reflexively and methodically about assumptions (particularly concerning the use of evidence to make sound judgements).
- Assess and evaluate progress in thinking evaluatively.

Background and Logic

Evaluative thinking is particularly critical for facilitators of multi-actor work but also participants. When we engage in evaluative thinking, we:

- Suspend judgement, considering alternative explanations and allowing new evidence to change our mind
- Question assumptions, particularly about the pathway of cause and effect
- Select and develop solutions that are informed by a strong evidence base and are responsive to our context and priorities
- Value the lessons we can learn from all our experiences? Disappointments as well as triumphs
- Wrestle with questions of impact and effectiveness, not just activity and implementation
- Maximise the value of existing data sources already available to us, mindful of their limitations
- Work to improve the strength of our evidence base as we go.

Source: [New South Wales Government Resources](#)

Evaluative thinking involves questioning assumptions, examining whether conclusions logically flow from findings and distinguishing opinions from factual evidence Quinn-Patton (2018). Evaluative thinking is similar to reflective practice and is a way to question, reflect and modify actions. It is increasingly recognised as a key component of high-quality evaluation practice. The logic and values of evaluation derive from the principles of systematic inquiry, logical reasoning and effective communication.

Use of a Self-Assessment template developed by Developmental Evaluation (DE) expert [Michael Quinn-Patton](#)¹ can be used periodically to support the facilitator to assess and map their progress in applying evaluative thinking.

Materials

- Reflective Journal
- Self-Assessment Template

1 This link leads to accessible infographics and a podcast explaining the DE approach.

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Before starting the facilitation process, the facilitator should get a reflective journal which they use to document the processes & learnings from their perspective.
- **Note:** while we refer to the facilitator's implementation of this self-assessment in this guide, actors/participants involved in interactive innovation can also use and benefit from this guide. It is particularly useful for actors considering to become a facilitator of interactive innovation.

Step 2: Document the Process

- As the interactive innovation process begins, each and every stage should be documented by the facilitator. Learnings (and false assumptions) should be included in the reflective journal.
- Any issues that arise with participants (e.g. conflicts or unities) or with the process (e.g. successes, 'lightbulb' moments, relationship-building, challenges, failures etc.) should be documented.
- How did the facilitator feel at that time? What actions would s/he take if the situation arose again? Any indications of how actors felt at that time and what actions they would take if the situation arose again?
- The reflective journal is for the facilitator's own personal use and is not typically shown to anyone else. When reflecting on the overall process, the facilitator has access to a clear and concise account of each stage of the process if 'mysteries' subsequently arise. They may use reflective diaries from one project to provide insights & learnings in facilitating another project. Using reflective practice aids the facilitator in their evaluative thinking.

Step 3: Completing the Self-Assessment Template

- The reflective diary is a source of information to accurately and reflexively complete the Evaluative Thinking Self-Assessment Template.
- A self-assessment template of practicing evaluative thinking - as presented below - can be completed by the facilitator.
- It is important that the facilitator answers the question honestly and openly to truly practice evaluative thinking.
- The facilitator may use the template periodically in order to assess and map progress in practicing evaluative thinking.
- Example of a completed Self-Assessment template on Practicing Evaluative Thinking. Template taken from Michael Quinn-Patton's book Facilitating Evaluation.

*Frequency: Always / Usually / Sometimes / Rarely/ Never

Principle	Explanation	Frequency*	Example of This Principle in Your Practice	Example of this Principle Absent from Your Practice
1. Be Clear	Be clear about goals and purposes; be clear about what's being evaluated, what data will be collected, what judgement are to be made, and how results will be used- indeed, be as clear as possible about everything	Usually	I was very clear with participants about my role in the process and my reason for being in[place]	I wasn't clear enough about the issues raised in relation to funding and at times allowed it to dominate the topic of conversation.
2. Be intentional	Know what you want to do and why. Plan your work and work your plan. Think through what you're doing. Consider contingencies	Usually	I was very purposeful in planning for each workshop, with the exception of the "first small steps" workshop. All other workshops were very-well planned with aims and objectives outlined. Very clear methods and techniques needed to achieve them were identified.	I was not fully prepared for the first workshop which I facilitated on my own. I was asked to facilitate on my own at short notice and did not feel fully-prepared going into the workshop.
3. Be accountable	Systematically examine the extent to which your intentions and hopes work out as planned and accomplish what you want to accomplish.	Usually	Throughout the process I kept my reflective diary which allowed me to reflect and examine each step of the process. After each action I was able to stop and reflect to determine if things were going in the right direction and how I felt about the process. Using DE techniques also allowed for participants to be accountable for their actions throughout the process (Gamble, 2018).	Within the process an individual may have mislead others into believing I had all the answers in relation to an Agri-Environmental scheme. I don't think I fully addressed this issue which led to one of the working groups becoming somewhat reluctant about seeking information about this elsewhere.
4. Be specific	Specificity is related to clarity; hone in on concrete and precise details of your work to enhance meaning and support effective communication	Usually	When it came to choosing the roles I was very specific and clear in explaining the type of roles that were required such as administrative roles that I had been carrying out for all of the groups in the earlier stages of the process. When engaging and incentivising the community I used methods of communication that were relevant to local people.	I made it very clear from the outset that one of my core values was to be very fair with people and to give everyone equal chances and opportunity's. One individual questioned that during the process and implied that I was not being fair and equal which I felt wasn't the case. I should have pulled him up on this issue in hindsight.

*Frequency: Always / Usually / Sometimes / Rarely/ Never

Principle	Explanation	Frequency*	Example of This Principle in Your Practice	Example of this Principle Absent from Your Practice
5. Focus and prioritize	Be purposeful in deciding what's worth doing and knowing; make decisions about priorities and own the consequences.	Usually	In the workshop where the groups were brainstorming and choosing their roles the Food Production Group were losing sight of the tasks and were having a very detailed discussion which was slightly off-topic. I had to be quite firm with them to remind them to stay on-task and once I raised the issue they focused on the task they were supposed to be carrying out	In facilitation I believe there is a boundary that you have to maintain to protect yourself during the process. If you do not respect this boundary you can easily become consumed by the process. At the beginning I was quite poor at maintaining this boundary between my research and me. It was something I should have prioritised more at the beginning.
6. Be systematic.	Organise and document all that is done. Engage logically, sequentially and comprehensively	Usually	I was very organised throughout the process and after each workshop all of the work that had been carried out on flipchart paper was transcribed onto a word document. This allowed for a record of all the work carried out throughout the process to be well documented and was easily accessible.	At one particular workshop I was not fully logical when I varied the headings used for group plans. The mistake was mine and I had to redo the workshop at a later date because of it.
7. Make assumptions explicit	Determine what can and cannot be subjected to empirical tests	Usually	Carried out willingness to pay survey and used hypotheses framework (Gamble, 2018)	
8. Draw conclusion based on evidence	Collect and use data to support finding and logical explanations for conclusions	Usually	When the issue was raised in relation to some of the groups capitalising on selling locally-produced food to tourists I put together a willingness-to-pay survey to conduct research to examine if visitors to [place] were willing to pay for locally-produced food.	

*Frequency: Always / Usually / Sometimes / Rarely/ Never

Principle	Explanation	Frequency*	Example of This Principle in Your Practice	Example of this Principle Absent from Your Practice
9. Be attuned to and adapt to complex considerations and implications	Watch for and adapt to what emerges, nonlinear effects, dynamic interactions and turbulence in complex dynamic systems	Usually	As the project progressed I was able to predict when trouble was going to arise and often was able to diffuse the situation before an issue arose.	When issues arose throughout the project with one individual I was able to use the skills I had developed to deal with situations there and then in a professional way. However, I was very poor at dealing with the situation on a personal level. I would take the bad behaviour and the cross words to heart and at times would spend a few days being slightly upset by it.
10. Think systemically	Examine interrelationships, perspectives and boundaries and their implications for evaluation.	Usually	I clearly identified early on that there were no cliques within the groups. This allowed the workshops to be very enjoyable and productive throughout the process for the most part.	At the beginning I may not have fully understood the relationship that the [actor] had with [organisation]. If I had examined this relationship further it would have made things clearer from me.
11. Make criteria and standards for judgements explicit	Identify, communicate and use clear criteria, values, and standards for judgements. Considerable decisions and sensible conclusions	Usually	Throughout the process I was fully aware that there were people involved in the project that I preferred, on a personal level, over others. I was very conscious of this fact so I ensured that I did not allow it to affect the research process	At times I was unsure as to what direction the project was going in. From workshop to workshop I was uncertain of what the next step was as I felt I didn't fully understand the process as it was my first time facilitating a project.
12. Limit generalisations and casual explanation to what data support	Align conclusions about possible generalisations and attributions of causality with the nature of the data being interpreted.	Usually	I never made generalisations in my mind about the people of [place]. I never considered them to be 'just sheep farmers'. I was always open-minded to their background views and opinions.	A number of times throughout the process generalised comments were made and I didn't correct them when perhaps I should have.

Principle	Explanation	Frequency*	Example of This Principle in Your Practice	Example of this Principle Absent from Your Practice
13. Be culturally sensitive and competent.	Engage with diverse segments of communities to include cultural and contextual dimensions important to the evaluation. Cultural variations and factor are critical to understanding.	Usually	I was very conscious at the beginning to take the time to get to know the people involved with the project as well as the landscape and area itself. The trip which I was brought on in [place] allowed me to get a true sense of the people along with the traditions and culture of the area.	When I distributed the leaflets into [place] for the Engagement Day I only printed them in English. Even though I was aware that parts of [place] were [language] speaking regions, I did not cater for this initially.
14. Be contextually sensitive	Pay attention to what is happening in the greater context and how it may be influencing your work. Adapt to the changing context as necessary/ possible	Usually	It was brought to my attention at the beginning that the [place] was divided "above and below the hill". To ensure that everyone was accommodated in the best possible way brainstorming workshops was held "above and below the hill".	When issues arose with a certain individual I began to feel some resentment towards the project and its participants. I was conscious of being professional and of concealing this from participants. I strove to maintain good relationships with them.
15. Be alert to the unanticipated consequences.	Don't just look for what you expect to see or planned to measure. Unintended consequences can be as important as those intended.	Usually	I was aware for a while that the group with an individual who caused a number of difficulties was not progressing. At times this individual's behaviour towards me in workshops did influence the progression of that group. As a consequence of this individual's behaviour and poor attitude towards me at workshops the progress made by that group may have been impeded.	When I made a mistake over a name in relation to the trip to [leading edge] I had no idea that the fallout would be so severe. It was an unintended consequence that I had not anticipated.

